

Western Mediterranean Sea Data Management Plan

Version 0.3

EMSO ERIC
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History of changes

Version	Date	Change	Author(s)
0.1	8/10/2021	First draft	Sara Pensieri, Roberto Bozzano
0.2	20/02/2023	Update with Erddap description	Sara Pensieri, Roberto Bozzano
0.3	15/12/2023	Update the template	Sara Pensieri, Roberto Bozzano

DMP Western Mediterranean Sea

Dataset Overview	
Dataset Title	Time series of the Western Mediterranean (W1M3A) research facility
Dataset Description	Meteorological, hydrographic, and biogeochemical time-series in the water column from 2014 from the Western Mediterranean (W1M3A) research facility.

Data Collection
<p>The Western Mediterranean Sea Regional Facility (RF) is a single multidisciplinary observatory located in the Western Mediterranean Sea with real-time and delayed mode capabilities.</p> <p>The RF is composed of a large spar buoy and a sub-surface mooring:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Surface buoy: includes the ODAS Italia 1 buoy located 80 nautical miles from the Ligurian coast on a seabed 1200 deep. The spar buoy was specifically designed for air-sea interaction studies and the collection of meteorological data even in rough seas. This station generates long-term meteorological and oceanographic time-series in the Western Mediterranean Sea. 2. Subsurface mooring: located close-by the main surface buoy, generates long term oceanographic time-series from 100 m down to the ocean interior. <p>The observatory provides data to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● study the connections between physics and bio-geo-chemistry along the water column on long-term offshore in the Western Mediterranean basin (Gulf of Genoa). ● study air-sea interactions in an area often characterized by a particular cyclogenesis. ● assess the climate variability in the marine environment. ● identify anthropogenic, geophysical, and biological sound sources and to evaluate their impact to the overall sound budget of the basin. <p>Measured variables</p> <p><u>Atmosphere</u></p> <p>Atmospheric pressure (8m asl), Horizontal wind speed, gust wind speed, wind direction relative to true North, air temperature in dry bulb, relative humidity, total incoming radiation, hourly precipitation rate, longwave incoming radiation (10 m asl).</p> <p><u>Ocean-Air interface</u></p> <p>Sea surface temperature (0 m)</p> <p><u>Water column</u></p> <p>Temperature, electrical conductivity, practical salinity (different depths)</p>

Turbidity, pCO₂, dissolved oxygen, chlorophyll-a fluorescence (6 m)
Underwater sound

Seafloor

None

Data format

UNIDATA netCDF files compliant with the netCDF Oceansites, Climate and Forecast (CF) metadata conventions as described in the EMSO ERIC Data Management Plan.

Services

Direct download from the portal www.w1m3a.cnr.it and through Erddap service at <http://erddap.w1m3a.cnr.it/>

Western Mediterranean Sea Data Policy complies with FAIR4 principles, and the data is available to users, openly.

Data Processing

The automatic process for creating the data files in netCDF format starts each day at 02:10 UTC.

The netCDF file has the following name format *OS_W1M3A_yyyymmdd_R.nc* and netCDF files are available for downloading to the Mediterranean In-situ TAC of CMEMS operated by the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR, Greece), on the web site of the observatory (www.w1m3a.cnr.it) in the section Download data and are also available through the ERDDAP server of the RF (<http://erddap.w1m3a.cnr.it/erddap/index.html>).

The near real-time data undergo automatic data quality control procedures compliant with WMO and OceanSITES standards.

After quality check, data are inserted into the near-real-time W1M3A MySQL relational database using java routines whereas PHP modules are used to query the database for accessing data and for visualizing the measurements.

Pre- and Post-deployment Procedures

The following table includes the list of the deployed sensors and the pre- and post-deployment procedures carried out to ensure high quality data.

Sensors	Variable(s)	Comment
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SeaBird SBE37sm (CT, CTD) SeaBird SBE16plus (CTD) SeaBird SBE39 (T) SeaBird SBE56 (T) RBR XR-420 (CT, CTD) RBR Concerto (CTD)	Temperature Salinity Pressure	Data quality is checked before each deployment by using a reference or a freshly calibrated instrument. In case of large differences, a service to the manufacturer is planned.
Wetlabs ECO-FLNTUS	Fluorescence Turbidity	Calibration is checked before each deployment by using reference standard samples.
SeaBird SBE43 SeaBird SBE63	Dissolved oxygen	Calibration is checked before each deployment by using an analytical laboratory probe and a Winkler analysis is performed on water samples collected on site the day of deployment.

After the recovery, sensors are maintained and all data are downloaded to be quality checked to avoid spikes, trends, abrupt change, etc.
Sensors showing drift or that have been deployed for more than two years are sent to the manufacturer for calibration.

Documentation and Metadata

The metadata are standardized into netCDF files, following the format conventions and standards defined by EMSO, as described in the EMSO ERIC Data Management Plan.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

Data of the Western Mediterranean research facility is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

Storage and Backup

Data recovered from self-recording instruments are quality checked and constitute a “delayed mode” dataset that is inserted into the delayed mode W1M3A MySQL relational database using java routines.

Selection and Preservation

All raw and quality-controlled data are backed-up on a private Network Attached Storage (NAS) for long-term archiving.

Data Sharing

Collected data are available in a graphical form on the portal of the observatory (<http://www.w1m3a.cnr.it/>) in the section “Near-real-time plots” under the “Data access” tab.

Daily and monthly data records in netCDF format are available to all users from the link http://www.w1m3a.cnr.it/OI1/modules/site_pages/download_netcdf.php.

All available data both historical and near real time are also freely available through the ERDDAP server of the RF at <http://erddap.w1m3a.cnr.it/erddap/index.html>

Data may also be available through external data services such as CMEMS, OceanSITES, Coriolis, EMODnet, and others.

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Responsibilities and Resources

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